

The combined effect of excess pressure and sphere shape on supercooling of tap water

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Abstract When a liquid reaches its freezing point or below it but remains liquid, we call it supercooling. Tap water contains impurity, which can act as a nucleation site for crystallization. That is why everyone uses pure water in a supercooling experiment. However, in this paper, we showed how we supercooled tap water using latex party balloons, where the freezer temperature range was from -10°C to -13°C . Moreover, we have shown how normal tap water can prevent from being crystallized by adding excess pressure and sphere shape.

Keywords Supercooling · Crystallites · Nucleation · Phase diagrams · Dendrites · Seed crystals

1 Introduction

It all started with my little sister Neela. Once, she was playing with party balloons. She filled one of the balloons with water and sealed. It was summer, and she loved to play with ice. So, she put that water balloon into our refrigerator. After a few hours later, when she brought it out, it was still liquid. She started to toss it and catch it like a ball, but suddenly she saw the liquid inside turned into ice. She got surprised and showed it to me. When I observed it, I understood that water inside the balloon was supercooled. However, I was confused because it was normal tap water inside the balloon, and it should already freeze. Then how it reached the supercooling state! So, it made me curious about doing detailed research on it.

Although there was already some research work on parameters that affect supercooling. In 1977, Gilpin showed in his paper how hot tap water supercool more than cold water [1]. Another research work showed that, for regular tap water, the nucleation temperature is usually $4-6^{\circ}\text{C}$ below freezing [2].

In this study, we studied the supercooling of tap water inside latex party balloons. The freezer temperature range was from -10°C to -13°C , and the initial water temperature was 32°C (room temperature). Our primary objective is to observe how long tap water can stay supercooling without being freeze inside a party balloon compared to the same water in a cup. And then, we analyze the surface tension effect on this experiment.

2 Experimental Setup

2.1 Tools

We used latex party balloons, commercial freezer, BMP180 high precision pressure sensor, Dallas DS18B20 temperature sensor, and some length measuring tools for this experiment.

2.2 Balloons Pressure Collection Set Up

First, we measured the current atmospheric temperature and pressure, which was 32°C and 1001mb. Then we took a party balloon and installed our pressure measuring sensor inside it. Then we inflated the balloon. We measured the pressure inside with a different radius. The inside pressure was higher than the pressure outside. Table 1 is showing the pressure change with different radius.

Table 1: Balloon Pressure Data at 32°C

Balloons Radius (cm)	Inner Pressure(mb)	Excess Pressure(mb)
2	1049	48
3	1040	39
4	1032	31
5	1025	24
6	1023	22

2.3 Samples preparation and set up

For this experiment, we took five latex party balloons. We named them B1, B2, B3, B4, and B5, where B means balloon. We filled them with different volumes of water, showing in table 2. The water we used was normal tap water. Then we took a cup made out of glass. We named it C1. We poured it with the same tap water. The amount of water that we put on this cup was (250ml) derived from those five water balloon's average volume. We did this part for a better compare freezing time between cup water and water inside those balloons.

Then we took another cup named C2 and placed a temperature sensor inside it. We poured it with the same amount of tap water that we poured in the C1 cup. The purpose of this second cup was to see how long it takes water to reach its freezing point. However, we avoided putting our sensor in the C1 cup so that our sensors did not affect our samples. Figure 1 is giving a better visual understanding of our setup. After that, we put those samples on a tray and placed them inside our freezer at -10°C.

Fig. 1: This is a visual expression of our experimental setup

2.4 Samples data

The effect of surface tension due to the water-latex and latex-vapor interfaces is negligible. To confirm that, we assumed all our samples were like big water droops without the latex balloons. That means they now have a liquid-vapor interface. Then we used this formula $\gamma_w = 235.8 \left(1 - \frac{T}{T_c}\right)^{1.256} \left[1 - 0.625 \left(1 - \frac{T}{T_c}\right)\right]$ mN/m given by IAPWS to calculate water's surface tension at a lower temperature [5]. Moreover, this surface tension data also matched with another research work done by Jan Hrubý, Václav Vinš, Radim Mareš, Jiří Hykl, and Jana Kalová [3]. Even though these data apply to the liquid-vapor interface for pure water, we assumed them for our tap water, as we mentioned above. This step is just for conforming to how slight the pressure can be due to surface tension.

Using our surface tension data and Laplace pressure equation [4], we calculated the excess pressure of water inside each of the samples. Table 2 shows the excess pressure of water for each of our samples.

Table 2: Samples volume, surface tension force and excess pressure data.

Name	Water Volume (ml)	Surface Tension Force(N)	Excess Pressure (pa)
B1	320	.02060	3.64
B2	285	.01982	3.79
B3	250	.01897	3.95
B4	215	.01804	4.16
B5	180	.01700	4.41

As we can see, the pressure due to surface tension for the liquid-vapor interface of our samples is minimal and negligible. So, we can assume the effect of surface tension due to the water-latex and latex-vapor interfaces are also negligible.

2.5 Deformed curvature area

When we put a balloon on a surface with water inside, the balloon's curvature deforms with a specific area. This deformed area depends on the water's weight. If a balloon contains much water, its circular curvature will deform more. Figure 2 shows this area. We measured this area for each balloon and calculated pressures on their deformed area using water's density, gravity, and balloons height, shown in table 3.

Fig. 2: Deformed curvature area of a balloon while on a surface

Table 3: The deformed area of our samples and the pressure there
{For roughly ($\rho = 997 \text{ kg/m}^3$) & ($g = 9.80\text{ms}^{-2}$)}

Name	Height (cm)	Deformed Area (cm ²)	Pressure on Deformed Area (pa)
B1	8.1	19.84	791.419
B2	8.0	18.20	781.648
B3	7.8	16.48	762.107
B4	7.4	14.58	723.024
B5	7.0	13.16	683.942

3 Observation

3.1 First phase

We divided our observations into two phases. The first phase observation was to see which one starts freezing first among all of the samples. At the beginning of our first phase, we observed water took 32 minutes to reach 0°C from its initial temperature of 30°C. We continued observing in every 30 minutes. After 1:26 hours later, freezing started in the C1 cup, and the water surface started to make a thin crystal layer. At that time, the water temperature was -10°C. On the other side, water inside those five balloons was still liquid.

3.2 Second phase

After 1:26 hours later, water in the cup started freezing, so our objective of this second phase was to see how long it takes water inside those balloons to freeze. Moreover, which one freezes first among the five of them. Surprisingly for eleven hours, there was no freezing. The freezer temperature was -13°C , and water was still liquid inside those balloons. Meanwhile, water in the cup became solid ice. We were still curious to see how long this will go. After 11:28 hours, we found the B1 balloon, which had the highest volume of water started freezing, and there was a thin layer of ice inside it. After 12 hours, we observed that some other balloons also started growing ice crystals inside them. Finally, 12:29 hours later, all of them had an ice crystal layer inside them. Although inside that ice layer, there was still liquid water. So, we decided to stop our experiment and started to observe the ice layers.

3.3 Ice crystal observation

We brought out all of the balloons outside of the freezer and ripped off the balloons to observe the ice layer. We saw that they all had hexagonal crystal ice, also known as “Ice one h” [6], as shown in figure 3a. However, in B4 and B5 balloons, there was dendritic crystal growth showing in figure 3b.

(a) Ice I_h

(b) Dendritic crystal growth

(c) Bottom view of fig.3a

Fig. 3: Ice that we found in our samples

We also noticed that hexagonal ice from B1, B2, and B3 had a hole on their bottom (figure 3c), and the bottom part of the ice, which was stick with the tray surface, was thinner than the top layer. Those holes were precisely on the bottom area where the balloons were touching on the tray surface.

4 Observational results

The objective of phase one was to see which one freeze first among the cup and balloons. That result is showing in table 4, also in figure 4.

Table 4: Freezing time of water inside the cup and balloons

Time (min)	Temperature (°C)	Freeze					
		C1	B1	B2	B3	B4	B5
32	0	No	No	No	No	No	No
86	-10	Yes	No	No	No	No	No

Fig. 4: Water temperature graph of our experiment

The objective of phase two was to see which one freeze first among all the balloons. That result is showing in table 5.

Table 5: Freezing time of water inside the balloons

Time (min)	Temperature (°C)	Freeze				
		B1	B2	B3	B4	B5
688	-13	Yes	No	No	No	No
704	-13	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
725	-13	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
738	-13	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
749	-13	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

5 Analysis

5.1 Phase 1 result analysis

We can see that water inside balloons stay supercooling for a more extended period from figure 4. On the other side, the same amount of tap water is freezing early in a cup. Both the balloons and the cup had the same tap water and were at the same temperature. The only parameter change between them was their excess pressure. Balloons are giving a sphere shape to water, which causes a uniform pressure distribution on the surface. From table 1, we see that balloon also giving some excess pressure inside. That means the total excess pressure that water has inside is water's excess pressure + balloon's excess pressure. However, water excess pressure is very negligible, so we only taking the balloon's excess pressure.

Water molecules try to make a hexagonal hydrogen bond when we freeze it; however, this excess pressure keeps water molecules, forming a hydrogen bond. As water is acting like a spherical water droop inside a balloon, it gives a uniform pressure distribution at the water's surface, which prevents from growing any nucleation point. As a result, water is staying in a supercooling state inside our balloons.

5.2 Phase 2 result analysis

Even though inside a balloon, the water stayed supercooling for a more extended period, they also freeze. However, this freezing time varies with different volumes of water as their total excess pressure is not the same. Table 6 shows that the balloon with a lower total excess pressure freezes first than the higher total excess pressure. Also, in figure 5, we can see how freezing time increases with the increase of total excess pressure.

Table 6: Total excess pressure and freezing time data of our samples

Name	Total Excess Pressure (mb)	Freezing Time (min)
B1	30.7934	688
B2	31.0379	704
B3	31.7755	725
B4	33.3136	738
B5	35.0201	749

Fig. 5: Total excess pressure graph of our experiment and the change of freezing time

Earlier, we saw the bottom part of ice was much thinner, but the top part was thick. Which means, the nucleation process started from the top surface. Water weight causes a deformed area under the balloon. This area has a higher pressure than the top surface, causing a pressure difference between the top and bottom surfaces. The bottom has a higher pressure than the top due to the height of the balloons. This pressure is high in the deformed area. Any point near this area also has pressure but lower than the pressure on the deformed area. The more we move away from the deformed area, the more the pressure decreases.

Moreover, at the top point, there is no pressure causing by water weight. That is the point where water molecules can easily make hydrogen bonds. That is why freezing started from the top part, and we found a thick ice layer on top. However, on the bottom, the ice layer was thin because of high pressure.

6 Conclusion

We studied supercooling of tap water inside latex party balloons. Our studies conducted that tap water can stay liquid below its freezing temperatures for a more extended period inside a balloon. Balloon's excess pressure and water's sphere shape causing by the balloon gives water a higher uniform pressure distribution that prevents growing nucleation points. Moreover, we observed that water with a higher weight deforms more surface area, which breaks the uniform pressure distribution. As a result, inside the balloon, water with a higher weight froze first than lower weight. In short, a balloon with much water inside has less excess pressure but high curvature deformation, which causes it to freeze early.

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